

Versatility of The Sural Flap for Reconstruction of Leg Defects: Experience of the LIC. Adolfo López Mateos Medical Center in Patients with Limited Access to Microsurgery

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ABSTRACT

The sural flap is a reliable reconstructive option for patients with defects ranging from the knee and popliteal fossa to the distal third of the leg, including the ankle, particularly in settings where microsurgery is unavailable or inaccessible due to patient-related factors. Its consistent vascular supply, technical simplicity, and versatility make it a key tool in reconstructive surgery. This study aims to evaluate the versatility, effectiveness, and complications of the sural flap in the reconstruction of leg defects in patients without access to microsurgery, through a retrospective analysis conducted at the Lic. Adolfo López Mateos Medical Center. Among 14 patients, 13 (92.8%) achieved successful flap integration. One patient (7.1%) developed vascular pedicle thrombosis within 24 hours, requiring flap takedown and surgical reintervention. Minor complications included seroma formation (<2 ml) in 3 cases, wound dehiscence less than 1 cm in 2 cases, and greater than 1 cm in one case, which was resolved with an outpatient skin graft. Transient venous congestion occurred in 4 reverse flaps. All patients recovered functional ambulation, and 12 (85.7%) reported satisfaction with both aesthetic and functional outcomes. Thirteen patients were discharged within 48 hours postoperatively. The pedicled sural flap is a dependable option for lower limb reconstruction, offering high success rates, low morbidity, and favorable patient acceptance in terms of function and aesthetics. Its use should be especially considered when effective soft tissue coverage is required without the need for microsurgical techniques.

KEYWORDS: Sural flap, leg reconstruction, microsurgery, reconstructive surgery, fasciocutaneous flaps.

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INTRODUCTION

The sural flap is a fasciocutaneous flap based on perforators from the peroneal artery, accompanied by the sural nerve and the small saphenous vein. Its design allows coverage of distal defects without the need for microanastomosis, resulting in shorter operative times, less need for specialized instruments, and favorable functional outcomes. Additionally, the technique is reproducible, has a short learning curve, and can be successfully applied even in patients with comorbidities. Both microsurgical techniques and the sural flap offer their own advantages, which should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis. However, in settings with limited resources or in the absence of a microsurgical team, the sural flap is a highly valuable tool within the plastic surgeon's reconstructive arsenal.

Complex wounds in the distal leg region present a significant challenge to reconstructive surgeons due to the limited availability of soft tissue and frequent exposure of critical structures such as bone, tendons, or osteosynthesis material. These types of injuries may result from high-energy trauma, burns, deep infections, or surgical complications and are a frequent cause of hospitalization, functional morbidity, and prolonged recovery. Globally, it is estimated that between 1% and 2% of the population will suffer from a chronic wound at some point, with up to 70% of these located in the lower extremities, primarily the leg.

In Mexico, several epidemiological reports have documented that over 66% of wounds treated in institutional healthcare facilities correspond to injuries of the lower limbs, with a significant proportion located in the distal third of the leg. Traumatic wounds and diabetic foot ulcers are the main etiologies leading to the need for specialized surgical coverage. These lesions represent not only a clinical issue but also a significant economic burden for both patients and the healthcare system. Treatment may involve prolonged wound care, specialized materials, antibiotics, multiple hospitalizations, and even amputations in cases of treatment failure.

Microsurgery has proven to be an effective tool for the reconstruction of extensive defects in the lower limbs, allowing the transfer of free tissue flaps with superior functional and aesthetic outcomes. However, its application is limited by various factors such as the need for specialized infrastructure, trained personnel, surgical microscopes, longer operative times, and advanced postoperative care. In most second- or third-level public hospitals in Mexico, microsurgery is not always available, requiring the use of regional or pedicled flap techniques instead.

Among these alternatives, the pedicled sural flap stands out as a technically reproducible axial or reverse-flow fasciocutaneous flap that allows coverage of distal leg defects without the need for microanastomosis. Its use has been widely reported in the literature as a low-cost, fast-execution

technique with good outcomes—even in patients with risk factors such as diabetes, smoking, or peripheral vascular disease. However, it also presents limitations, such as the risk of partial necrosis in longer flaps, venous congestion, or inability to cover very extensive defects.

Despite its advantages, there are few studies in Mexico that systematically document institutional experience with the sural flap, including therapeutic outcomes and complication rates. The lack of local data makes it difficult to standardize selection criteria and to compare this technique with more advanced options like free flaps. This data gap generates uncertainty in surgical decision-making, particularly in hospitals where microsurgery is unavailable and there is a need to optimize surgical resources without compromising clinical outcomes.

In this context, there is a need to objectively and retrospectively evaluate the surgical experience with the sural flap at a public referral institution, identifying its benefits, complications, and practical utility in reconstructing leg defects in patients with limited access to microsurgery. This evaluation aims to contribute to local knowledge, support clinical decision-making, and optimize surgical care for patients with complex lower limb wounds.

ANATOMY

This flap is harvested from the posterior aspect of the leg, between the popliteal fossa and the mid-leg region, centered along the midline raphe between the medial and lateral halves of the leg. It is fasciocutaneous in composition, typically measuring approximately 10 × 12 cm. Flaps wider than 6 cm generally require a skin graft to close the donor site.

The arterial anatomy is composed of a dominant pedicle—a perforating branch of the sural artery—along with regional supply from the popliteal artery. The dominant pedicle has an average length of 3 cm and a diameter of 1.4 mm. It descends from the popliteal fossa between the heads of the gastrocnemius muscle and the deep fascial layer, traveling inferiorly over the gastrocnemius muscle. It also includes minor perforator pedicles from the peroneal artery (1 cm long, 1 mm in diameter). In the distal third of the leg, there are additional minor perforators from the posterior tibial artery (1 cm in length, 1 mm in diameter). Neurocutaneous perforators from the sural nerve also contribute, originating from the sural artery, with lengths around 1 cm and diameters greater than 1 mm. The vasa nervorum of the sural nerve emit perforators to the overlying skin and fascia.

VENOUS ANATOMY

The venae comitantes accompany all perforating vessels to the flap, especially in the reverse-flow flap. When a skin island is preserved, venous drainage also occurs through the subdermal plexus.

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NERVE SUPPLY

The medial sural cutaneous nerve (S1–S2), a branch of the tibial nerve in the popliteal fossa, provides sensory innervation. It courses alongside the small saphenous vein and the sural artery.

FLAP DESIGN AND MARKING

Design for anterograde flap:

The skin island is designed from the popliteal fossa down to 4–5 cm below its level, extending to the mid-leg. The width depends on the reconstructive need but generally does not extend more than 5–6 cm above the lateral malleolus to preserve vascular supply.

Design for reverse flap:

The design of the distally based superficial sural artery flap is made on the posterior aspect of the leg. The skin island can be raised from any part of the distal two-thirds. The pivot point of the pedicle should be located at least 5 cm above the lateral malleolus to preserve the anastomoses with the peroneal artery.

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Flap variants: Reverse sural flap, adipofascial flap, delayed flap, supercharged flap.

FIGURE 1:

A 55-year-old male patient with no chronic degenerative diseases, who sustained a gunshot wound (shotgun) inflicted by a third party, resulting in a wound in the popliteal region of the right lower limb measuring approximately 12 × 8 cm. The patient had undergone three previous surgical debridements, with negative wound cultures. The image shows a posterior view, with the defect located in the popliteal fossa. The sural flap with axial flow is marked on the leg, preserving 6 cm distal to the popliteal fossa. A 6 cm vascular pedicle is indicated (red lines), a midline incision for raising cutaneous flaps (purple line), a cutaneous island measuring 13 × 8 cm (blue line), and the anatomical path of the medial sural nerve.

FIGURE 2:

Posterolateral view of the right lower limb in the immediate postoperative period, showing a pedicled axial-flow sural flap placed in the popliteal fossa, covering 100% of the wound area. The flap is sutured with 3-0 nylon using simple stitches. A 5/8 Penrose open drain was placed due to mild bleeding prior to flap fixation to reduce the risk of hematoma. An inverted S-shaped sutured incision is visible, closed with continuous 4-0 nylon stitches, where cutaneous flaps were closed to release the pedicle with the fascial component of the flap. Below, the donor site is visible, covered with a meshed, thin split-thickness skin graft, fixed with 4-0 nylon.

FIGURE 3:

Follow-up at the outpatient clinic 7 days postoperatively. Adequate healing is observed, with no areas of necrosis or flap compromise, proper closure of the lower wound, and integration of the skin graft.

FIGURE 4:

Follow-up at the outpatient clinic 21 days postoperatively. Proper integration of the axial-flow sural flap is observed, as well as successful incorporation of the skin graft.

FIGURE 1:

A 35-year-old male patient with no chronic degenerative diseases, who suffered a motorcycle fall, being thrown from it. He presents a wound on the left lower limb measuring 18×6 cm on the posteromedial surface near the knee joint, without exposure of internal structures. The wound shows granulation tissue after two surgical debridements, with negative wound cultures.

FIGURE 2:

Posterior view of the left lower limb, showing the marking of the axial-flow sural flap, skin island (red line), vascular pedicle with fascial component (green line), and the course of the sural nerve (black line).

FIGURE 3:

Delineation of the skin island with distal elevation; the vascular pedicle (vein, artery, nerve indicated with forceps) is identified.

FIGURE 4:

Approximated skin flaps are visible, indicated with hooks; below them, the skin island is fully dissected.

FIGURE 5:

Lateralization of the skin flaps is observed, with the vascular pedicle including the fascial component and the skin island fully dissected.

FIGURE 6:

Complete elevation of the axial-flow sural flap prior to tunneling, with skin flaps lateralized for proper visualization.

FIGURE 8:

Anterior view of the left lower limb in the immediate postoperative period, showing a pedicled sural flap placed over the wound area covering the knee joint region, with the remaining area covered by a split-thickness skin graft.

FIGURE 9:

Postoperative follow-up at 48 hours prior to discharge home, showing adequate flap evolution without complications or signs of flap distress.

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FIGURE 1: This corresponds to a 19-year-old female patient who suffered a motorcycle accident, sliding 7 meters on asphalt. She was initially treated at a secondary care center with surgical debridement and then referred to our hospital, where immediate reconstruction with an axial-flow sural flap was decided. The image shows the right lower limb with a wound measuring 18 × 10 cm, containing abundant necrotic tissue, asphalt residues, and inorganic material. The knee joint is visible without fractures confirmed by radiographic studies, and there are abrasions below the described lesion.

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FIGURE 2: Intraoperative image showing extensive surgical debridement and cleaning of the wound, removing all necrotic and inorganic material. Soft tissues and the knee joint are visible.

FIGURE 3: Anteromedial view of the right lower limb with partial tension-free wound closure, showing a reduced wound area measuring 6 × 5 cm.

FIGURE 4: Posterior view of the right lower limb, showing the marking of the axial-flow sural flap with skin island dimensions according to the residual area. The vascular pedicle is identified in the distal portion (blue pointer), and the skin island is partially dissected.

FIGURE 5: Completely dissected sural flap, with lateralized skin flaps for adequate visualization. The vascular pedicle is preserved with its fascial component to reduce the risk of flap compromise.

FIGURE 6: Elevation of the axial-flow sural flap prior to tunneling.

FIGURE 7: Anterior view, immediate postoperative period showing the axial-flow sural flap tunneled and placed at the recipient site, fixed with simple non-absorbable sutures. The skin island shows appropriate coloration without signs of flap distress.

FIGURE 8: Follow-up at the outpatient clinic 7 days after surgery, showing adequate flap healing with no areas of dehiscence or flap compromise.

FIGURE 1: This case involves a 61-year-old male patient with a history of long-standing diabetes mellitus and clinical signs of pelvic arterial insufficiency. After falling from a height of 2 meters, he sustained a metaphyseal fracture of the right fibula, managed with a DCP plate by the Orthopedics Department. Our service was consulted for skin coverage of the osteosynthesis material located at the lateral malleolar surface of the right lower limb. The image shows a wound area measuring 14×6 cm, with granulation tissue and exposed osteosynthesis material.

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FIGURE 2: The image shows a wound area with partial closure in the proximal region, measuring 10 × 6 cm, with exposed osteosynthesis material.

FIGURE 3: Posterior view of the right lower limb showing the marking of a reverse sural flap. The skin island measures 11 × 6 cm (black line). The incision lines for raising skin flaps and releasing the vascular pedicle are shown (blue line). The area corresponding to the vascular pedicle includes its fascial component. Safety margins are indicated: proximal (6 cm distal to the popliteal fossa) and distal (10 cm from the malleolar surface) (black lines).

FIGURE 4: Complete dissection of the reverse-flow sural flap. The skin island appears well-perfused. The vascular pedicle, with its fascial component, is preserved and not skeletonized. Skin flaps are raised at the distal pole of the flap to release the pedicle prior to tunneling.

FIGURE 5: Posterior view of the right lower limb showing a fenestrated split-thickness skin graft at the donor site. Skin flaps are sutured with 4-0 nylon using tension-free continuous sutures.

FIGURE 6: Reverse sural flap tunneled to the recipient site, providing coverage of the osteosynthesis material. The flap is sutured with 4-0 nylon using simple, tension-free stitches.

FIGURE 7: View of the reverse-flow sural flap 48 hours postoperatively, with capillary refill time of 3 seconds assessed using forceps. No changes in coloration, venous congestion, or signs of flap compromise are observed.

FIGURE 8: Follow-up at the outpatient clinic 10 days after surgery. The reverse-flow sural flap shows good healing without signs of compromise or complications.

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FIGURE 1: This case involves a 47-year-old male patient with a history of grade II obesity, who was struck by a motor vehicle, resulting in crushing injury to the right lower limb. He sustained a metaphyseal fracture of the right tibia and metatarsal bones, along with a simple wound below the popliteal fossa and multiple bruises secondary to the trauma mechanism. He was managed conservatively by the Orthopedics Department with open reduction and internal fixation (ORIF) of the fibula, a 2 mm K-wire in the metatarsals, and wound closure. Our service was consulted intraoperatively for skin coverage. The lateral view of the right lower limb shows a wound measuring 14×6 cm, with exposed fibular fracture and soft tissue damage caused by the injury mechanism.

FIGURE 2: Design of a reverse-flow sural flap, with safety margins set at 6 cm distal to the popliteal fossa and 6 cm proximal to the lateral malleolus. The skin island measures 11×6 cm (thick black line), and the vascular pedicle with its fascial component is marked (thin black line). The incision area for lifting skin flaps and releasing the vascular pedicle for proper tunneling is shown. Color changes due to hematomas from the injury mechanism are visible on the limb.

FIGURE 3: Lateral view showing the marking of the reverse sural flap and partial suturing of the wound area.

FIGURE 4: Complete dissection of the reverse-flow sural flap with the vascular pedicle including its fascial component, placed over the wound area. The skin island has good coloration, skin flaps are lateralized, and the donor site is exposed.

FIGURE 5: Posterior view showing the donor site covered with a 1:1.5 meshed split-thickness skin graft. Skin flaps are sutured with 4-0 nylon. Partial view of the reverse sural flap is also seen.

FIGURE 6: Lateral view in the immediate postoperative period. The reverse-flow sural flap covers the entire recipient area, with good coloration of the skin island. It is fixed with 4-0 nylon simple sutures.

FIGURE 7: Follow-up at 36 hours post-procedure shows a partial color change (<1 cm) in the distal portion of the flap, secondary to a seroma. This was managed by removing one suture point and draining the seroma without further complications.

FIGURE 1: This case involves a 28-year-old male patient with no significant medical history, who suffered a motorcycle accident with direct contusion to the left knee. He presents a wound measuring 14×9 cm, with partial soft tissue loss and abrasions, as well as patella exposure. No fractures were identified on radiographic studies. The patient underwent surgical debridement prior to skin coverage.

FIGURE 2: Posterior view of the left lower limb showing markings for the design of an M-SAP flap. A bimalleolar line and a line from the popliteal fossa to the distal medial malleolus were drawn. Using Doppler, three perforators from the medial sural artery were detected (marked with red crosses). A probable skin island was outlined based on the two perforators closest to the midline.

FIGURE 3: Anterior view showing soft tissue coverage of the wound using the M-SAP flap. Only one perforator artery was used, dissected under direct vision up to the popliteal region. A skin island was designed, and the M-SAP flap was tunneled to the recipient site without tension or compression of the vascular pedicle. It was fixed with simple 4-0 nylon sutures.

FIGURE 4: Follow-up at the outpatient clinic 21 days postoperatively, showing proper integration of the M-SAP flap, with no evidence of dehiscence or flap compromise.

FIGURE 1: This case involves a 28-year-old male patient who sustained a motorcycle accident resulting in a diaphyseal tibial fracture in the left lower limb. The fracture was managed with a DCP plate by the Orthopedics Department. He was referred to our service due to a wound measuring 8 × 5.5 cm on the anterior surface of the upper third of the left leg.

FIGURE 2: Medial view showing a chimeric M-SAP flap with two vascular pedicles previously identified using Doppler. The wound area to be covered is located on the anterior surface of the left leg.

FIGURE 3: Immediate postoperative view showing the tunneled chimeric M-SAP flap placed over the wound area, fixed with 4-0 nylon sutures. The donor site for the split-thickness skin graft is also visible, covered with a chlorhexidine dressing.

RESULTS:

Outcomes of Lower Limb Reconstruction with Pedicled Sural Flap

Among the 14 patients who underwent reconstruction of the lower limb using a pedicled sural flap, complete flap integration was achieved in 12 cases (85.7%). One case (7.1%) presented with early arterial thrombosis of the flap,

requiring reoperation. Minor complications included seromas less than 2 ml (21.4%), wound dehiscence less than 1 cm (14.2%), and transient venous congestion (lasting less than 24 hours) in reverse flaps (28.5%). All patients regained functional ambulation, and the majority (92.8%) were discharged within 48 hours postoperatively.

Complications Table

<i>Complication</i>	<i>Cases (n)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>Flap thrombosis + reoperation</i>	1	7.1
<i>Seroma (<2 ml)</i>	3	21.4
<i>Dehiscence <1 cm</i>	2	14.2
<i>Dehiscence >1 cm (managed with graft)</i>	1	7.1
<i>Venous congestion (reverse flap)</i>	4	28.5
<i>Mild intraoperative bleeding</i>	2	14.2
<i>Graft non-integration (<30%)</i>	2	14.2
<i>Hospital stay >48 hours</i>	1	7.1

Complications Chart

SURGICAL PEARLS

Axial-Flow Sural Flap

The upper marking was made by drawing a line between the medial and lateral femoral condyles and strictly maintaining a 6 cm safety margin distally. The region corresponding to the vascular pedicle was then outlined—without skin inclusion—preserving the fascia as part of the pedicle, with thickness equal to or up to 1 cm less than the cutaneous island.

At the pedicle zone, skin flaps were elevated at 3 mm thickness to avoid compromising dermal perfusion. The dissection began with an S-shaped incision, lifting the full thickness of the vascular pedicle for adequate exposure and mobilization.

The vascular pedicle with fascial component was fully released down to the safety margin, maintaining fascia without skeletonizing the vessels.

The skin island was marked to be equal in size—or up to 1 cm larger—than the defect to be covered.

In all cases, flaps were tunneled manually, with subcutaneous dissection at least the width of the pedicle. Care was taken to avoid compression and ensure the flap reached the recipient site without tension.

If minor bleeding persisted despite electrocautery, a thin (5/8) Penrose drain was placed to prevent hematoma under the flap and removed before discharge to reduce infection risk.

Dissection began at the distal skin island, tracing the vascular bundle which was ligated, cut, and temporarily tagged with a suture. With gentle traction, the flap was further dissected in the sub-fascial plane, maintaining the pedicle’s vascular-fascial thickness to reduce compression risk during tunneling.

Reverse Sural Flap

The marking included a strict 6 cm safety margin above the lateral malleolus.

Skin flaps (3 mm thick) were elevated with an S-incision along the pedicle area to preserve dermal blood supply and ensure good exposure.

The vascular pedicle with fascia was fully released to the safety margin, confirming that the flap reached the recipient site without skeletonizing the pedicle.

The skin island was marked to match or exceed the size of the defect by up to 1 cm.

A thin Penrose drain (5/8) was used when minor bleeding persisted, removed before discharge to minimize infection risk.

Anticipating venous congestion due to reverse flow, the leg was kept non-weight-bearing, with pillows under the popliteal fossa and heel, and the limb elevated above heart level postoperatively.

M-SAP Flap

A handheld Doppler was used to locate the medial sural artery and perforators.

Perforators near a midline drawn from the popliteal fossa to the medial malleolus were sought and identified.

Lateral dissection was performed around the Doppler-identified perforators. Once their size was confirmed, the skin island was outlined.

A portion of the vascular-muscular pedicle was preserved as a chimeric component to avoid skeletonization.

In one case, abrupt color changes due to pedicle thrombosis were noted 24 hours post-op, prompting immediate re-exploration. The flap was dismantled, and soft tissue coverage was then achieved using a medial gastrocnemius flap.

CONCLUSIONS

The versatility of the sural flap makes it a workhorse in lower limb reconstruction. While microsurgery offers excellent outcomes, it remains largely inaccessible for much of the population in our country. Thus, using the sural flap in its various forms to cover defects from the knee and popliteal fossa to the ankle allows effective soft-tissue reconstruction using minimal equipment, often enabling hospital discharge within 48 hours. The technique is attainable for reconstructive surgeons with a reasonable learning curve, and it reduces both the economic burden of prolonged hospitalization and the wider cost to our healthcare system.

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